

Cover

Article: Advancing the adoption of oncology decision support tools in Europe: insights from CAN.HEAL

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Frederickx N, Froyen G, Kamal M, Dupain C, Pallocca M, Maetens J, von Bubnoff N, Ciliberto G, De Wurstemberger P, Chamoun Morel Z, Alessandrello R, McCrary JM, Maes B, De Maria R, Nowak F, Castellano-Garcia JM, Prats C, Giacomini P, Hebrant A, Raicevic Toungouz G, Van den Bulcke M and Van Valckenborgh E (2026) Advancing the adoption of oncology decision support tools in Europe: insights from CAN.HEAL. <i>Front. Digit. Health</i> 8:1784519. doi: 10.3389/fdgth.2026.1784519</p> <p>https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/digital-health/articles/10.3389/fdgth.2026.1784519/full</p>
<p><i>Abstract</i></p>	<p>Effective cancer care increasingly depends on digital decision support tools (DSTs) to interpret complex clinical, molecular, and genomic data and guide personalised treatment decisions. However, the oncology DST (oncDST) landscape remains fragmented, with limited interoperability, inconsistent standards, and uneven clinical adoption across healthcare systems. This fragmentation hinders routine clinical use and impedes the demonstration of robust clinical benefit. To address these challenges, the CAN.HEAL consortium proposes the EU-oncDST digital framework, a conceptual, harmonised, interoperable, and modular architecture designed to integrate existing oncDSTs across Europe. Developed through consortium-wide consultations, an EU-level survey and comprehensive mapping of both public and private solutions, the framework provides a practical pathway for implementing interoperable oncDSTs while fostering stakeholder collaboration and innovation. At its core, the framework empowers Molecular Tumour Boards (MTBs) to operate efficiently at institutional, national, and European levels. Early phases focus on piloting and validating oncDST use within MTBs, optimising patient-centred consultations, harmonising variant annotation, and enhancing clinical trial matching. Overall, the EU-oncDST digital framework aims to provide a practical and collaborative pathway to strengthen oncology decision-making and accelerate the translation of precision medicine into clinical benefit across Europe.</p>